

Assigning Parole

April 28, 2026

1 Description

A district court, CourtOnYourDistrict, determines prison sentences based on the risk of re-offending, with longer sentences for prisoners at high risk of re-offending.

1) **CourtOnYourDistrict relies on employees to assess a prisoner's risk of re-offending.**

- a) Imagine you are a prisoner of CourtOnYourDistrict. How acceptable do you find it when an employee assesses the risk of re-offending?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- b) Please describe a situation where using employees would be beneficial for assessing the risk of re-offending.
- c) Please describe a situation where using employees would be harmful for assessing the risk of re-offending

An organization, TechForLeagal collects data on wealthy prisoners, including the nature of their offenses, their criminal history, their mental health, their employability, behavioral changes, and parole officer recommendations.

TechForLeagal uses the collected data to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict whether a prisoner will re-offend.

2) **Instead of employees, the CourtOnYourDistrict now relies on TechForLeagal's AI to assess a prisoner's risk of re-offending.**

- a) Imagine you are a prisoner of CourtOnYourDistrict. How acceptable do you find it when an AI assesses the risk of re-offending?
 - i) completely unacceptable

- ii) somewhat unacceptable
- iii) neutral
- iv) somewhat acceptable
- v) completely acceptable

- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be beneficial for assessing the risk of re-offending.
- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be harmful for assessing the risk of re-offending.

3) **Consider that CourtOnYourDistrict relies on TechForLeagal’s AI to assess an applicant’s risk of re-offending and determine their prison sentences. TechForLeagal identified an issue with its AI that employees could exploit the AI to disadvantage blue-eyed prisoners by giving them a longer prison sentence, even though these prisoners have a low risk. To address this, TechForLeagal modifies the AI to mitigate the issue.**

- Please describe how this ‘AI modification’ could be beneficial for everyone.

Modifying the AI has some side effects, which are described as different scenarios in parts (a), (b), (c), and (d). Please indicate your preference for the following scenarios:

- a) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that it incorrectly predicts longer prison sentence for low risk prisoners. It is impossible to completely protect the AI manipulation by the employee and still provide correct prison sentences for low risk prisoners. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLeagal to choose?**
 - i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and it provides highly correct prison sentences.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and it provides slightly incorrect prison sentences.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and it provides moderately incorrect prison sentences.
 - iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and it provides highly incorrect prison sentences.
 - Give an example of potential issues if TechForLeagal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- b) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that CourtOnYourDistrict can learn whether a prisoner is wealthy by identifying if they were part of TechForLeagal’s data. It is impossible to completely protect the AI from manipulation and still**

prevent CourtOnYourDistrict from identifying prisoners is wealthy. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLeagal to choose?

- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and it has no chance to reveal whether the a prisoner is wealthy.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and it has a slight chance to reveal whether the a prisoner is wealthy.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and it has a moderate chance to reveal whether the a prisoner is wealthy.
 - iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and it has a high chance to reveal whether the a prisoner is wealthy.
- Give an example of potential issues if TechForLeagal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- c) **The above modification of the AI has made it possible for CourtOnYourDistrict to determine the number of women in TechForLeagal’s collected data. It is impossible to completely protect the AI from manipulation and protect information about the number of women. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLeagal to choose?**
- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and it has no chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and it has a slight chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and it has a moderate chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and it has a high chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
- Give an example of potential issues if TechForLeagal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- d) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that CourtOnYourDistrict’s employees can easily learn the information of the participants that TechForLeagal used to build the AI. It is impossible to completely protect the AI from manipulation while preventing information learning. In this scenario, if you were a prisoner, which option would you suggest for TechForLeagal to choose?**
- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and there is no chance to learn the information used to build the AI.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and there is a slight chance to learn the information used to build the AI.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and there is a moderate chance to learn the information used to build the AI.

- iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and there is a high chance to learn the information used to build the AI.
 - Give an example of potential issues if TechForLeagal chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

2 Demographic Information

- 1) What is your gender?
 - Man | Woman | Non-Binary | Prefer not to answer | Self-describe [text input]
- 2) Do you identify as being part of any minority groups?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 3) What age group do you belong to?
 - 18-25 | 26-35 | 36-45 | 46-55 | 56-65 | Prefer not to answer
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - Less than a high school degree | High school degree or equivalent [Non-university education beyond high-school (technical college, community college, vocational education) | Some college, no degree | Bachelor's or Associate's degree | Master's degree | Doctoral degree | Prefer not to answer
- 5) Are you a practitioner (researcher, working professional) in Artificial Intelligence?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 6) Please provide your Prolific ID, this is important to get the compensation.